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**NARRATING DEVIANCE: A PSYCHOANALYTICAL STUDY OF
SELECTED PRE- AND POST-PANDEMIC FICTION BY
CATHERINE RYAN HOWARD**

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Abstract

This is a psychoanalytical study based on the fictional constructs of a renowned thriller writer Catherine Ryan Howard, of the contemporary world. It works on the theory of psychoanalysis, which is the study of unconscious mental processes and is described as depth psychology. It was proposed by the Austrian psychiatrist Sigmund Freud at the start of the twentieth century. Under the broad spectrum of this theory, and the selected crime fiction, Firstly, this research investigates the two parallel spheres; pre- and post-pandemic fiction, to analyze deviance that is the root of crimes and criminal mindsets, to further investigate how Catherine Ryan Howard engages with the lockdown and its effects on the human psyche, and how it has filled the minds of her characters with frustration, fear, conflicts, and anxiety that has led them to get involved in brutal acts. Secondly, it studies how Howard's characters become more insecure and paranoid. Thirdly, this research performs a comparative study of the characters of both novels to validate the stance that the urge to commit crimes rises during the period of lockdown as it brings social distancing, zero physical interaction, loneliness, despair and fear of dying through hunger or by contracting the disease. It further analyzes the effects of lockdown on the fictional selves, with contemporary fiction's role in registering the pandemic's impacts on the human psyche. Furthermore, through close reading, this research reflects Freud's psychoanalysis that the conflict between id, ego, and super-ego causes individuals to commit atrocious criminal acts, and later, due to the fear of punishment, they behave like pseudo-moralists. Finally, the role of societal institutes is also looked upon as they play their part in suppressing crime-involved activities for restoring social order in society.

1. INTRODUCTION

The contemporary world is identified with a lot of crimes and criminals on the daily basis, so writers take it as a great opportunity to write with the intention of highlighting crimes in society; making people more aware of the consequences of it or restoring a social order by making the criminal go under a trial. On the other hand, there are writers like Anthony Burgess who amusingly presents criminal activities. His popular novel *The Clockwork Orange* mocks the trials and judicial system in society and shows a very distressing overview of crimes in a highly comic way. So, crime has become a part of writing for quite some time now, but its representation is wholly dependent on the circumstances, and on the intentions of a crime-fiction writer. It is said that crime fiction impacts the readers' psyche and works as a therapy; a 'distractive therapy' for them. Most people escape from their real-life problems and hurdles by reading crime fiction.

It is said that literature mirrors everything that happens in society. For centuries, literature has been covering all the movements, historical events, plagues, and everyday activities. Therefore, in the year 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic hits almost the whole world. It was said to be the noxious viral infection after the Spanish flu that has caused millions of deaths around the globe. During this time,

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pandemic literature starts popping up. It covers the stories of coronavirus and how it has affected human life and hindered the normal functioning of society. It challenges not just human health, but it has greatly impacted societies economically, socially, and politically.

Catherine Ryan Howard is a popular crime fiction writer from Ireland and has been writing since 2016. Her debut novel *Distress Signals*, her latest novel *The Nothing Man*, and *56 Days* mark as the best thriller novels of 2021. However, *56 Days* is a riveting story of first encounters, hidden secrets, and confined spaces” (Jessica 2021). It narrates life under COVID-19 restrictions and how it has really affected and disturbed the normal functioning of human beings. On the other hand, *The Nothing Man*, the other novel of this dissertation tells the story of a criminal Jim in the pre-COVID world. This whole research is a comparative study of the two criminals Jim and Oliver in two opposite affairs. It studies the default of both the protagonists on the individual as well as on the societal levels; to study the reasons for their criminal affairs and how the lockdown has contributed to it. It also includes the three subfields of the theory of psychoanalysis which further assists in the deeper analysis of the selected fiction in a very profound and focused way. The four subfields are psycho-criminology, psychodynamics, behavior, and cognition. These four dimensions study psyche, childhood traumas, behaviors, and mental processes, respectively.

The progression in the novel reveals that Oliver is a convicted child murderer and is hiding his criminal acts to be an innocent guy. Therefore, the theory further investigates the dysfunction in his personality that led him to his death at the end of the novel. As far as, *The Nothing Man* is concerned, it tells a tale of a murderer who is famous as ‘the nothing man’. He has looted and killed many families and houses, but his ill fortune starts from there when he robbed a house and murdered, everyone, except Eve. Luckily this girl of nearly twelve years survived and now she is grown up and decides to take revenge by knocking him red-handed. “I was the girl who survived the *Nothing Man*. Now I am the woman who is going to catch him” (Howard, 2021, p. 38).

1.1 Significance of the Study

The study critically explores the nature of criminals and their mindsets. It focuses on the selected crime fiction by Howard. It critically analyses different events, scenarios, and characters to detect the reasons behind the criminal behavior of Oliver and Jim. It configures the consequences of lockdown and its impact on individuals. The theoretical framework of this research is an amalgam of psychoanalysis and criminology. It was proposed by Sigmund Freud and later developed by many theorists and psychoanalysts named Franz Alexander, August Aichhorn, Melaine Klein, and Fritz Redl. This research takes an opportunity to address the crimes committed during the lockdown times and before the lockdown. However, it does a comparative study to highlight the intensities and rates of criminal activities.

1.2 Problem Statement

A psychoanalytical study is made to explore the personality, psyche, and fears of individuals who commit heinous crimes. It particularly studies the nature of crimes during the time of lockdown and investigates the reasons behind an increase in domestic violence. Moreover, it studies how the lockdown during COVID-19 and, normal circumstances has contributed to the increase in criminal behavior of individuals. A brief analysis is also done to explore the mental disorders, stress levels, and fears of such criminals in order to prevent society from further violence, and massive bloodshed, and also to devise new effective ways to tackle such pandemics and their unhealthy outcomes.

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1.3 Research Objectives

To analyze the nature of crime in the two parallel worlds: pre- and post-pandemic. To explore contemporary conditions like fear, isolation, and social distancing as they are becoming a source of the rise in crime rates. To learn about the transformation of individuals through their past criminal acts. To highlight the role of social institutions in restoring a social order.

1.4 Research Questions

How are the prime elements of psychoanalysis justified by the protagonists of the novels? How are contemporary conditions, like isolation, fear, and social distancing are becoming a reason for the rise in criminal acts? How have Freud and Alexander analyzed the crimes and the criminal mindset? What are the roles of societal institutions in restoring social order?

2. Literature Review

Catherine Ryan Howard is a crime writer from Cork, Ireland. Her recent novel titled *56 Days* was marked as the best thriller by the Washington Post, the New York Times, and by the Irish Times: “At or near the top of any list of superb Irish thriller writers these days is Catherine Ryan Howard, an Edgar nominee for ‘The Liar’s Girl’ in 2018. Her fifth stand-alone, the masterly ‘56 Days,’ is set mostly during a 2020 coronavirus lockdown in Dublin and brings two vulnerable and insecure 20-Something’s together for an anxious, pandemic-limited, let’s-see-how-it-goes romance” (Richard, 2021).

Crime by the Book (2021) writes a blog and reviews the novel *56 Days*. The blog further states that “it’s tense, claustrophobic, and wholly original.” She gives the plot details along with the language analysis. “It’s an expertly-crafted blend of domestic suspense and murder mystery”. She also narrates how COVID-19 perfectly fits into the backdrop of the story.

Franz Alexander and William Hailey (1935), write a book named *Roots of Crime: Psychoanalytic Studies*. This book states a psychoanalytical study of eleven criminals. These criminals have mental disorders. Hence, this book states that mental disorder is the real reason behind criminals coming up with heinous crimes. Thus, mental disorders contribute in making a personality dysfunctional.

Jen Ryland (2021), while reviewing *56 Days*, has analyzed the ambiguous character of the protagonist and child murderer Oliver. He talks about the brilliant narrative techniques in the novel to add suspense and thrill to the story. He also highlights how the pandemic has made the investigation very tough.

Michael Foucault (1975) writes the book *Discipline and Punish*. It is a history of the modern penal system. Foucault seeks to analyze punishment in its social context and to examine how changing power relations affect punishment. This book helps this research in explaining its stance how whether it is important to restore social order and if yes, then is it restored through punishment.

Sigmund Freud (1923), writes a remarkable book *The Ego and the Id*. He elaborates on the human psyche with the help of his theory of psycho-dynamics of the Id, Ego, and Super Ego. As, he famously put it 10 years later, “where Id was, their ego shall be.”

Stanton Samenow (2014) writes a book named *Inside the Criminal Mind*. In this book, he explains the vast patterns of criminal minds and focuses on the most common crimes, for instance, domestic violence, terrorism, and internet victimization. He also explores drug abusers and gives remarkable solutions to such problems and pulls out ways to control crime in society.

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Sinead Crowley (2020), writes a brief review of the book *The Nothing Man*, a thriller novel written by Catherine Ryan Howard. “A book within a book and a character study with real depth, *The Nothing Man* takes the current obsession with true crime and amateur detectives and wraps it around a gripping plot.” She gives a plot summary and rates it as the best summer reading with a lot of twists and turns. This research is exceptional and original. The above-given literature review shows different writers’ views on the selected crime novels. However, my theoretical framework or lens, involving the current pandemic, is very unique in terms of its utility and for research purposes. No one has researched COVID-19 and its impact on the violence rate of a community through crime novels. Therefore, this research has filled the gap and ensures a more realistic amount of knowledge for the readers.

3. Methodology

This research is qualitative, descriptive, and interpretative in nature. The data is collected through different articles, book reviews, journals, newsletters, and YouTube videos made on the selected fiction by Catherine Ryan Howard herself. This research is carried out based on the ideas supported by the theory of psychoanalysis, whose founder was Sigmund Freud. Different elements of the personality and psyche of the protagonists are also interpreted through Alexander’s psychocriminology. Both the novels; *56 Days* and *The Nothing Man* are read critically, and all the given events, situations, and characters are well-analyzed to draw constructive comparative analyses to view specific details to further support the topic sentence of the research. A brief language analysis is also made to ensure well-managed and balanced research. COVID-19 and its consequences are also stated to support the questions of this research.

4. Discussion and Analysis

The Nothing Man is a crime novel written by Catherine Ryan Howard. The story revolved around a serial killer who had mugged and murdered five different houses and killed several people, most of whom were women. Media always reported about him but failed to recognize him and gave him the name nothing man because no one could ever prove anything about him, because he was too smart that he left no clues and no marks at the place or people on which he attacked.

At the time of the attack, Eve was twelve years old, and the assassin killed her father, mother, and her little sister Anna. Luckily, Eve survived the nothing man’s attack and now she was grown up and wanted to find the murderer of his family. Eve decided to write a book named, *The Nothing Man* so, she could catch him. The book got published and came out to the public and it went viral. On the other hand, Jim Doyle, a security guard at the supermarket was enthralled by the cover of the book because he was the nothing man himself.

This paper deals with a psychoanalytical aspect of the novel *The Nothing Man*, to examine the nature of crimes in the per-lockdown world. However, the other novel, *56 Days* was set in a period of lockdown. There were crimes, detectives, and investigation processes, all were carried out under strict COVID SOPs, and this did not just delay the process of investigation, but it also turned the criminal act into an unsolvable mystery till the end of the novel. On the other hand, in *The Nothing Man*, there was no perception of isolation, social distancing, contagious environment, etc. all the events happened in a lockdown-free world, without any restrictions.

Firstly, under psycho-dynamics, the past, of the individuals who commit crimes, played a very vital role in determining their future as it had impacted their whole life. The same happened with the antagonist of the novel *The Nothing Man*, his parents were separated, and he saw a loveless, broken

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relationship between his parents. Jim's father murdered his wife and then killed himself too. Jim had witnessed this brutality with his own eyes. Also, when he was between seven to fourteen years old, he was taken care of by a babysitter named Jean and she sexually mistreated fourteen-year-old Jim, which filled his mind with frustration and stress.

Deviance is present in everyone said by Alexander in his book, "criminal (antisocial) tendencies exist in all human beings because of the universal conflict which revolves around the Oedipus situation, the cornerstone of psychoanalytical theory" (Alexander, 1931). A person's good or bad behavior is decided by his surroundings, relationship with his family matters, and his personal life happenings, "the living experience of each individual in determining the kind of behavior responses which emerge" (Alexander, 1931).

In the early years of his adulthood, he became a serial killer because of his frustration and immoral nature. He started looting and murdering families. His major target was women. He used to rape them and then murder them. He committed all these murders in 2000 and the last was in 2001, the same year his daughter was born. And from there he left all his vicious activities. However, Eve came up with her book, *The Nothing Man* which made Jim remember all that he had done in the past, his case reopened, and authorities started to reconnect all the puzzles left years back and tried to find him again with the help of Eve's book.

4.1 Freud's Explanation of Crimes and Criminals

Sigmund Freud is the early founder of psychoanalysis and psychoanalytical theory. This theory is also used as a framework for many later studies. However, this paper deals with psychoanalysis and criminology to determine the reasons behind crimes and criminals' mindsets. As it is studied under psychoanalysis, human personality has three building blocks: id, ego, and super-ego. According to Freud's psychoanalytic theory: "The id is the primitive and instinctual part of the mind that contains sexual and aggressive drives and hidden memories, the super-ego operates as a moral conscience, and the ego is the realistic part that mediates between the desires of the id and the super-ego" (McLeod, 2021).

Id' is the unconscious setting of the mind. It works on the pleasure principle (Freud, 1920). On the other hand, the ego is the only conscious part of the human mind. It works on the reality principle. The ego is 'that part of the id which has been modified by the direct influence of the external world' (Freud, 1923, p. 25). 'Freud made the analogy of the id being a horse while the ego is the rider. The ego is 'like a man on horseback, who has to hold in check the superior strength of the horse' (Freud, 1923, p. 15).

Thirdly, the Super-Ego is the unconscious element of the human mind. It works on the morals, values, and norms of society. It is the self-triggering and warning sense. The super-ego has two systems: the conscience and the ideal self. The conscience is the inner voice that makes a person realize immediately if one has done wrong, the feeling of guilt. Secondly, the ideal self reflects the imagination.

Alexander explores in his famous book *Roots of Crime: Psychoanalytic Studies* that there is a relationship between childhood experiences and future criminal behavior. He elucidates that criminal behavior is because of a lack of proper development. Be it on an emotional, physical, psychological, or sexual level. In this novel, *The Nothing Man*, Jim's past or childhood experience was doleful. He noticed a loveless and broken relationship between his parents. He was taken care of by a babysitter Jean, who was a motherly figure for him but of course, she was not her real mother and Jim got

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attracted to her physically. This incident really jammed Jim and made him a misogynist. His ego was hurt. That is why, in his later years, he started to rape women and kill them.

On the other hand, in *56 Days*, Oliver St Ledger had a horrible childhood experience, where he ended up murdering his junior school fellow and this incident changed his whole life, “That he is Oliver St Ledger, Boy B from the Mill River case, notorious child murderer” (p. 194). He shared this tragedy of his past with her girlfriend Ciara. “A long, long time ago, when I was very young, when I was just a child, I was involved in something that . . . that I deeply, deeply regret. That I should never have done. That I wish I hadn’t every single moment since” (p. 211).

It was Oliver who had basically killed Paul, but he told Ciara the other way. He lied to Ciara that it was Shane who had killed him and that he was with him. However, in extreme pain and guilt, he told her the truth in the end that he murdered Paul, not Shane. “It was me. It was me. All . . . me. Not Shane.” Her hands release him, and he falls away, drops his head back to the ground” (p. 287). This incident really impacted Oliver’s personality and future as well. He became depressed and violent. He started taking anti-depressants and one day, under severe stress and pain, he killed himself by hitting his head on the washroom floor.

In a nutshell, Sigmund Freud under psychoanalysis analyzes human personality as well as the human psyche to detect the major reasons behind a crime or a criminal mindset. He defines psychoanalysis as the study of the unconscious mind. Then, they are conflicts between id, ego, and super-ego that leads to criminal behavior. As he assumes that the human personality has three main components: id, ego, and super-ego and if the id overpowers an individual’s psyche, he becomes a criminal in the future or near future. So, Jim and Oliver both were criminals and highly violent due to their weak personalities and horrific childhood upbringing and experiences.

4.2 Alexander’s Analysis of Crime and Criminals

After psychoanalysis, Alexander, an American psychoanalyst comes up with the theory of psychocriminology, which is basically a blend of psychoanalysis and criminology. It aims to explore how individual criminal behavior is acquired, evoked, maintained, and modified through personality, social, and/or environmental influences (Frontiers, 2022). However, Alexander’s book *The Criminal, the Judge and the Public*, classifies criminals on the basis of the reasons and causes of their violent acts. For instance, Chronic criminals, Neurotic criminals, Normal criminals, and Accidental criminals. It is said that Alexander retains a certain independence from Freud, viewing disturbed human relations, rather than disturbing sexuality, as the main cause of neurotic disorders (Britannica). Whereas normal criminals are like Jim, who is normal, but because of some disturbed human relationships and dreadful past experiences, is highly violent and threatening.

Under psychoanalytical criminology, this also comes under the heading of juvenile delinquency, which is a condition where an individual less than eighteen years commits a crime, and here Eve was only eleven years old when she accidentally murdered her father. On the other hand, in *56 Days* Oliver and Shane were also under eighteen years old. Both were around fifteen and sixteen when they killed Paul. Their case was also reported under juvenile delinquency: “Everything happened really quickly after that. We were charged and sent to Oberstown—it’s a juvenile detention center. There was a trial. Our identities had to remain a secret so we became Boy A and Boy B. We were both found guilty of murder” (p. 227).

Furthermore, Alexander talks about neurobiological causes as well that become a prominent reason for individuals to become criminals in the future. According to this study, it is said that there are some

criminal genes that are present in criminals that descend from their fathers or forefathers. This proves true in the case of Jim as his father murdered his wife too when Jim was young and later his father committed suicide. This aggression was building in him since early adulthood age when he was teased by Jean and later, with a wounded ego, he kept killing women so he could take revenge and could satisfy his ego and mental state. In *56 Days*, there were no neurobiological reasons found. It was more about trauma and horrible childhood memories.

Conclusively, Jim was a depressed, ignored, and broken person who needed love and attention but because of his parent's broken relationship and killing history, he became highly violent. Eve, along with the senior investigator of his case, Ed Healey had planned to catch Jim red-handed because they knew that after reading the book, he will try to find out Eve and try to kill her too. This time, he could not escape because his wife had learned about all his vicious plans, and she reported him to the police. Therefore, Jim was shot dead by the agencies and with the help of Eve and Noreen, they were able to locate and tracked down, the most famous serial killer in Cork.

4.3 Exploration of Crime in the Post-lockdown World

56 Days is a riveting story of first encounters, hidden secrets, and confined spaces (Jessica, 2021). It depicted a mystery tale of a young man named Oliver, who was new in Dublin city and the city was going through a lockdown. Ciara, the female protagonist of the novel was a secretive journalist and Oliver was a convicted child murderer. Both lied to each other and had not revealed their true identities till the end of the novel, which made it mysterious. As it said, "Secrets are a different thing. They're destructive. Secrets are destructive" (p. 85).

A twist came in the story when a virus hit the city and the city had to go under complete lockdown, and because of the fear of losing this newly developing relationship which was very uncomfortable, they decided to move in together. It was said that it would last for only two weeks but who knew at that time that it would last for more than two months: "He had thought the timing of their meeting was a gift from the universe to make up for all it had taken away from him in the past . . . the only way to keep seeing the man you've just met was to move in with him" (p. 201).

They moved in together and things started getting worse. Oliver's actions and behavior foreshadowed that he was hiding something from Ciara. He was also seeking therapy sessions from Dr. Dan as well because he was feeling that he might have some mental issues after that horrible incident. "It was all getting too much. He was maxed out on lies. And he absolutely hated telling them to Ciara" (p. 202). According to psychoanalysis, a criminal has fears of revealing his true personality, which is very much obvious in Oliver's case "he'd spent his whole adult life protecting his real identity. Someone else might dismiss it as a mix-up or mistake, but he wouldn't. And then he'd be on high alert" (p. 241).

Categorically, Oliver's past was very tragic and had horrible memories from it. Whatever he was showing and revealing, it was a shadow of his past. His fear reflected his past. His personality reflected dysfunction and several fears related to his past. He was always less confident, fearful, and restless, particularly, when he was around Ciara. The anxiety and guilt of his past acts, along with the fear of contracting the disease and unavoidable circumstances, made him attempt suicide which was intentional but becomes accidental, and he killed himself "it's an accidental death. The end" (p. 292). In fact, he was unable to face Ciara and his guilt anymore, whereas the lockdown pushed him to take such a decision, as no one was there to help him fight the anxiety he had been facing for last two weeks.

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4.4 Role of Society in Restoring Social Order

Benjamin, in his book *Toward the Critique of Violence*, says that only a state has the right to inflict punishment upon someone if he/she is found guilty of it. This is a legal duty of the state and here, the state is an institution of society, and it plays a very vigorous role in restoring social order by working towards law-making and law enforcement policies. As J. William Fulbright also says, “Law is the essential foundation of stability and order both within societies and international relations”.

Here, in *The Nothing Man*, a group of detectives plays a very crucial role till the end of the novel to find the nothing man and to punish him for what he had been doing for so long. However, he was caught and shot dead. They shot him dead as a punishment for his past criminal acts. Here, another very important institution played its role, family. Jim’s wife, Noreen played a role in making him caught by the police. She did not want that Kattie also became violent, out of frustration, like her father. However, under psychoanalysis, criminals don’t want to get caught or punished. So, they try their best to hide their true selves, because of the fear of punishment. Hence, punishment is a way to control crime.

In *56 Days*, a team of senior or junior investigators Karl and Lee was seen playing their role in solving the mystery of Oliver, despite the lockdown. They went to the crime scene and investigated each person, keeping in mind all the SOPs. However, this showed their determination despite the fear of COVID, and it was clearly reflected as a hurdle in the interaction and investigation process. The lockdown not only made the lives of Oliver and Ciara difficult, but it challenged the social investigation systems as well.

In a nutshell, societal institutions influence how society is regulated and facilitates the functioning of social systems. They contribute in both ways, in making society functional or dysfunctional as well. There are higher authorities that are working as institutions and make laws then there are family institutions that also promote morals and values to make individuals responsible than deviant in nature. Freud also concludes that society creates mechanisms that assist in restoring social order.

5. Conclusion

It is said that whatever is happening in the world greatly impacts literary works. Contours of global disasters, specifically, have always made their way into literary works. Similarly, COVID-19 was the deadliest viral infection contracted by the whole world and it surpassed the death toll of the Spanish flu. This disease not just affected human health but also impacted individuals psychologically, economically, and physically. Therefore, with the aim of getting away with all their worries, especially related to finance, they became aggressive as Catherine Ryan Howard depicted in her novel *56 Days*.

The novels of the dissertation, however, are unique in nature as they give an altogether different worldview. They zoom into the individual lives of people, especially of the deviants. *The Nothing Man* shows how the pre-COVID world helps a deviant to blend into the dynamic society. *56 Days*, on the other hand, shows the effects of the globally enforced lockdown on the deviant minds who could escape their own past by blending into society without any hesitation, but now had to face the long-escaped reality by confronting themselves in seclusion.

A parallel comparison of both novels and the deviant characters in them shows that the environment heavily influences the minds. In *The Nothing Man*, it is all about the critical growing-up phase of a person (Jim in this case) with the usual social settings of pre-lockdown. He does not face his traumatic

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inner self like Oliver has to, in lockdown times. Secondly, Jim has become deviant because of his id. He has nothing to do with external factors. Neither, he has any fear or guilt for his acts, however, on the other hand, Oliver is caught up by the upsetting conditions of the lockdown and becomes more paranoid and depressed.

Freud and Alexander have been monumental in understanding the primary thresholds affecting the minds and their probable patterns of committing crimes. Critical models of both psychoanalysts converge onto one overarching theme that both the culprits have had a past of violence that greatly manipulates their current lives. Oliver cannot get rid of the superego which constantly irks his self-imposed invented story of murder, while Jim's broken past never leaves him as it emerges in form of his frustration and resultant murders or by victims somehow coming in front of him to haunt his deviances.

Moving further, it is also observed that fear is a pervasive element in both novels. Both killers do not really face any morally constructed images of fear. They only fear the probable wrath of the law, a corporeal manifestation of fear in the form of corporal punishments. However, in the lockdown, thanatophobia was found in the characters and particularly, of Oliver which made him so suffocated and traumatized that he took his own life.

All in all, the paper focuses on the stark differences between the pre- and ongoing lockdown world in the stories. The complexities of lockdown not only take a toll on the dynamic social world in the form of controlled movements but also on the internal world of the characters. The conflicted past that Oliver emerges out as horrible as one can imagine. He dies in his bathroom, and his dead body decomposes there for the next two weeks because of the no-social-contact policies. Jim was also caught red-handed by the authorities and shot dead on the spot.

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